

THE INFLUENCE OF SOIL RETAINING NITROGEN-FIXING BACTERIA AND THE APPLICATION OF FOSSTIM-3 BIO FERTILIZER ON QUALITY INDICATORS OF SOYBEAN

Jahangir Khamdamov Usmanalievich

Research Institute of Grain and Legumes

Researcher of the Fergana Scientific Experiment Station

Tel;+99891-326-13-92

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Abstract: In this article, it is stated that different differences were found between the soil containing the bacteria and the bacillus subtilis bs-26 bacteria on the changes in the quality parameters of the soybean grain.

Key words: Soybean, varieties, nodular bacteria, soil, productivity, FOSSTIM-3, bacillus subtilis bs-26

Introduction: In recent years, great attention has been paid to the cultivation of soybean as the main crop in irrigated areas and to increase grain yield, grain quality, oiliness level and fertility of soils with low fertility in our republic. In paragraph 3.3 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021" important tasks aimed at significantly increasing the export potential of the sector" have been defined. At the same time, widespread introduction of resource-saving technologies based on the biology of the soybean plant in the cultivation of soybeans in our Republic is one of the urgent tasks of today.

By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3144 of July 24, 2017 and No. PQ-2832 of March 14, 2017 "On measures to organize soybean planting in the republic in 2017-2021 and increase the cultivation of soybean crops" No. PQ-2832 Decree No. PQ-3144 on amendments and additions to the Decree, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 of October 23, 2019 "On approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" and other regulations related to this activity - in the implementation of the tasks defined in the legal documents, conducting research on the soybean crop in our Republic is the basis for ensuring a high yield from this crop.

Level of study of the problem: A.Yu. Khadikova, A.E. Basieva, T.K. Lazarov, S.Kh. Dzanagov (2011), on the basis of the research conducted in the leachable black soils of Kazakhstan, noted that the use of mineral fertilizers N30P30K30 - N90P90K90 helps to increase grain yield and protein content. The best option turned out to be the combined application of mineral fertilizer N30P30K30 + 20

tons/ha of local fertilizer (manure). The use of fertilizers has a positive effect on the chemical composition of soybeans, in particular, on the increase in protein content and the collection of protein and oil per hectare.

S.G. Smirnov, M.M. Nafikov, V.N. Fomin (2014) The results of field experiments conducted in the Zakamya region of the Republic of Tatarstan showed that the highest yield of soybeans in years with normal moisture (up to 22-24 cm) after plowing formed when nitrogen N60 is applied against the background of phosphorus-potassium fertilizers. An increase in nitrogen rates from 30 to 90 kg of rates contributed to an increase in grain protein content from 1.0 to 1.6%

A.V. Dozorov and others (2019) stated that in conditions of leachable black soils of the Middle Volga region, the indicators of protein and oil content of soybean USXI 6 grain increase with an increase in the rate of mineral fertilizers. In the studies, the protein content of the control (without fertilizer) variant is 25.25%, the oil content is 18.46%, the protein content of the N20P20K20 variant is 26.32%, the oil content is 19.28%, the protein content of the N40P40K40 variant is 28.8%, the oil content is 23.83 %, the N60P60K60 variant had a protein content of 30.70% and an oil content of 24.92%.

Nitrogen fertilizers are widely used to increase the yield of cereal crops and the protein content of legumes. However, it is necessary to optimize their use to reduce the risk of environmental pollution and production costs .

Increasing the accumulation of nitrogen in plants, not by increasing nitrogen fertilizers, but by creating genotypes with the ability of their root system to absorb nitrogen from the soil, remains the main task in solving the problem. On the other hand, in order to obtain high rates of grain yield, this process must be accompanied by an increase in the activity of photosynthesis. Otherwise, it will lead to high concentration of nitrogen in grain and stem with reduced nitrogen use efficiency It is well known from the scientific literature that the influence of cultivation conditions and applied agrotechnical measures on the quality indicators of agricultural crops plays an important role. In our research carried out during

2019-2021, we also conducted a laboratory in order to determine the effect of the agrotechnical measures applied to the options on the protein and oil content of the grown soybeans. In our research carried out during 2019-2021, grain samples taken from variants were analyzed in laboratory conditions in order to determine the effect of agrotechnical measures applied to variants on the content of protein and oil content of cultivated soybeans.

Research results the results of the analysis show that when analyzing the varieties planted with the seeds of the "Baraka" variety of soybeans, it was observed that the protein content of the grain grown in the control variant 1, where the seeds were planted in the traditional way, was 32.7%, and the oil content was 23.1%, in which 1000 kg/ha of soil was taken from the 0-15 cm layer of the soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) along with the planting of soybean seeds. When analyzing the content of grain grown in the 2nd variant, the protein content was 33.3%, the oil content was 23. showing 8%, compared to the control 1-variant, the amount of protein in the grain increased by 0.6%, the amount of oil by 0.7%, Soybean seeds were treated with Fosstim-3 biopreparation at the rate of 1.0 kg/ha before planting, and 1500 kg/ha of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) was taken from the 0-15 cm layer and used during the growing season. Serhosil biofertilizer was sprayed in the form of a suspension at the rates of 10 l/ha in combs and 10 l/ha in pods.

When the chemical composition of soybeans grown in the 3rd option was determined, the protein content was 33.9%, and the oil content was 24.5%. Compared to the control soybeans grown in the 1st option, the soybean seeds were planted in the traditional way, the protein content was 1.2%, and the oil content was 1. 4%, before sowing soybean seeds, treated with 10 kg of soil taken from the 0-15 cm layer of soil containing nitrogen-fixing (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) fungi and 1.0 kg of Fosstim-3 biopreparation.

When analyzing the composition of grain grown in option 4, the protein content is 33.0%, the oil content is equal to 23.5%, and the control, the seeds of which were sown in the traditional way Compared to grain grown in option 1, the protein content is 0.3%, the oil content is 0.4%, along with sowing soybean seeds, 1000 kg/ha of the 15-25 cm layer of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) when the content of the grain obtained from option 5 applied to the seed was checked, the protein content was 33.1%, the oil content was 23.6%, compared to the control option 1, the protein content was 0.4%, and the oil content was 0.5% ha, before planting soybean seeds, treated with Fosstim-3 biopreparation at the rate of 1.0 kg/ha, and along with seeding, 1500 kg/ha of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) was applied in the amount of 15-25 cm of soil, and When studying the content of grain grown in variant 6, which was used in the form of a suspension of Serhosil biofertilizer at the rate of 10 l/ha during the growing season and 10 l/ha during podding, it was found that the protein content was

33.4%, the oil content was 24.0%, and the control was white compared to the 1st option 10 kg of soil taken from a 15-25 cm layer of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) and 1.0 kg of Fosstim-3 biopreparation Soybean grain grown in the 7th variant treated and planted with the analysis showed that the protein content was 32.9% and the oil content was 23.3%, compared to the control variant 1, the protein content was 0.2% and the oil content was 0.2%. was noted to be higher than In the experiment, the seeds of soybean variety "To'maris Mman-3" were sown, and when the quality indicators of the crop obtained from the cultivated variants were analyzed, it was observed that the above laws were repeated. %, oil content was found to be 24.3%, compared to this control option, in the 9th option, 1000 kg/ha of soil was taken from the 0-15 cm layer of the soil containing nitrogen-fixing (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) budding bacteria along with planting soybean seeds. When the chemical composition of the cultivated grains was checked, the protein content was 33.9%, the oil content was equal to 24.8%, the protein content was 0.7%, and the oil content was 0.5% compared to control 8-variant, which was sown conventionally. ha, soybean seeds are treated with Fosstim-3 biopreparation at the rate of 1.0 kg/ha before sowing, and azo t-collecting (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) was collected from the 0-15 cm layer of the soil and applied in the amount of 1500 kg/ha and during the growing season When analyzed, the grain harvested from option 10, which was sprayed with Serhosil biofertilizer in the form of a suspension at the rates of 10 l/ha in combs and 10 l/ha in podding, showed a protein content of 35.4% and an oil content of 25.3%, compared to control option 8. protein content by 2.2%, oil content by 1.0%, 10 kg of soil taken from the 0-15 cm layer of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) and 1.0 kg of Fosstim-3 biopreparation before sowing soybean seeds When studying the content of soybeans grown in the 11th option treated and planted with by 0.2%, with sowing of soybean seeds, nitrogen accumulator (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) 1000 kg/ha of soil was taken from the 15-25 cm layer of the soil containing bacteria, and the content of soybean grains grown in the 12th option was analyzed, and the protein content was 33.6%, and the oil content was 24.7%. compared to the grain obtained from the control 8 option, the amount of protein was increased by 0.4%, and the amount of oil was increased by 0.4%. together with nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) was grown in the 13th variant, which was obtained from the 15-25 cm layer of the soil in the amount of 1500 kg/ha and during the growing season Serhosil biofertilizer was applied in the form of a

suspension at the rate of 10 l/ha in combs and 10 l/ha during podding. when the chemical composition of the grains was checked, the protein content was 35.0%, and the oil content was 25.0%, compared to the control 8-variant, the protein content was 1.8%, and the oil content was 1.8%. and 0.7%, before sowing soybean seeds, treated with 10 kg of soil taken from a 15-25 cm layer of soil containing nitrogen-fixing (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) fungi and 1.0 kg of Fosstim-3 biopreparation. When the grain samples obtained from option 14 were analyzed, the protein content was 33.4% and the oil content was 24.4%, respectively, compared to the control grain grown in option 8, the protein content was 0.2% and the oil content was 0.1%. was observed to be high.

Research results: From the results obtained from the experimental options, it can be seen that the chemical composition of soybeans was positively affected by the use of soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) and, in addition, Fosstim-3 biofertilizer. From 0.2% to 1.2%, the oil content from 0.2% to 1.4%, and in the "Tomaris Mman-3" soybean variety, the protein content in the grain from 0.2% to 2.2%, oil it was found that the amount was ensured to be higher than 0.1% to 1.0%. In the studies conducted in 2020 and 2021, it was observed that the above laws were proven, and high results were obtained in the cases where soybean seeds were treated with Fosstim-3 biopreparation before planting, soil containing nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium japonicum*) was used, and Serhosil biofertilizer was sprinkled in the form of a suspension during the growing season. was found to have been received.

References:

1. Khadikov A.Yu., Basiev A.E., Lazarov T.K., Dzanagov S.Kh. Vliyanie urovney pitaniya na urozaynost i kachestvo zerna soi na vyshchelochennyx chernozyomakh // Izvestiya Gorskogo gosudarstvennogo agrarnogo universiteta. 2011. No. 2. – S. 48-50.
2. Smirnov S.G., Nafikov M.M., Fomin V.N. Vliyanie sposoba osnovnoy obrabotki pochvy i udobreniy na agrofizicheskie svoystva pochvy, urodajnost i kachestvo zerna soi // Sovremennye problemy nauki i obrazovaniya. 2014. No. 1. – S. 384.
3. Dozorov A.V., Kulikova A.Kh., Zakharov N.G., Naumov A.Yu., Khayrtdinova N.A. Udobrenie soi na chernozeme vyshchelochennom Srednego Povolzhya. International agricultural journal. 2019. 4 (370).– S. 76-79. DOI: 10.24411/2587-6740-2019-14071.
4. Le Gouis J., Fontaine J.X., Laperche A., Heumez E., Devienne-Barret F., Brancourt-Hulmel M., Dubois F., Hirel B. Genetic Analysis of Wheat Nitrogen Use Efficiency. Coincidence Between Qtl for Agronomical and Physiological Traits.

Proceedings of the 11th International Wheat Genetics Symposium, 2008.
Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/2123/3217>.

5. Hirel B., Le Gouis J., Ney B., Gallais A. The Challenge of Improving Nitrogen Use Efficiency in Crop Plants: Towards a More Central Role for Genetic Variability and Quantitative Genetics Within Integrated Approaches. *J. Exp. Bot.*, 2007, vol. 58, - P. 2369-2387.

